

NANOFACTS

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1. Overview

The purpose of this document is to provide an **overview of lectures and workshops that occurred during the training school event in topics related to cancer biosensing diagnostics, organized within the NANOFACTS project**. In cooperation with the project partners, Trinity College Dublin (TCD), Ireland, The School of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences and Vienna University of Technology (TUW), Faculty of Technical Chemistry, Institute of Applied Synthetic Chemistry and Institute of Chemical Technologies and Analytics, the BioSens Institute (BIOS), Serbia organized the specific NANOFACT event **Training School in nanoparticles, their application in cancer treatment, imaging and sensing**.

The Training School event was organized in M18 of the Project, **comprising lectures and practical exercises as an open event in the period between the 27th of June and 1st of July 2022 at the BioSense Institute Rectorate Building & Science & Technology Park and at the laboratories of the Biosense Institute in Novi Sad, Serbia**.

Since cancer represents a significant health challenge in Europe, the application of nanotechnology in medicine offers new opportunities to overcome the drawbacks of conventional therapy and develop optimized therapeutic and diagnostic tools. Therefore, the NANOFACTS training school provided a **transfer of knowledge** from project partners, invited speakers and international experts to Ph.D. students, researchers, and young professionals on **scientific advances related to the development of microfluidic, magnetic, and optical biosensors** for cancer, as well as in the **development of nanomaterials for targeted therapy and imaging of cancer**. **Clinical and surgical aspects of cancer treatment and new knowledge about cancer biomarkers** were also conveyed during the sessions. In addition, **lectures related to soft skills** with the purpose to **enhance the basic skills of researchers**, such as creative thinking, teamwork, and **problem-solving skills** were delivered. Finally, **lectures related to writing scientific project proposals, project implementation, and start-up management** were aimed at enhancing the self-sustainability of researchers. Due to COVID19 outbreak, all the activities were carried out in accordance with health and safety measures.

The conditions of the COVID-19 outbreak led to significant shifting in the organization of this event, but that did not affect its importance and realization, as well as its impact on the project implementation. In order to boost presence at Training School, we have made particular attention to designing an effective dissemination strategy through and promoting the NANOFACTS event on our Website and Social media platforms. Different promotional materials were prepared and distributed to the various target groups of targeted researchers and students with the aim to endorse their specialization in this topic and ensure the critical mass of prominent researchers that will contribute to the development of the knowledge-based society.

This report summarizes the activities related to the organization and realization of the NANOFACT Training School in cancer biosensing, including both theoretical and practical training. In this report, the following segments will be presented in detail: presented topics at NANOFACT training schools, abstract of lectures, introduction notes about presenters, schedule, list of instruments, models, and tools used during presentation and training, number of participants, statistics and other relevant data.

2. NANOFAC TS in Nanoparticles, their application in cancer treatment, imaging and sensing

2.1. Organization and preparation of training schools

In the project proposal, NANOFAC TS Training School (TS) event was planned for the first year of the project at M10. The duration of the whole TS was planned to be one week, consisting of 3 days of lectures, followed by 2 days of WSs. TS was planned to comprise lectures and practical exercises - Workshops (WSs). Lectures were planned to be open to the public, while WSs were planned to be limited to BIOS researchers. TS lectures on the first three days would give a broad overview of the subjects with the participation of TUW and TCD experts and invited speakers from supporting institutions and prominent researchers, while the WS lectures were planned to be given solely by experts from WUR and TCD.

Due to the COVID19 outbreak, lockdown, and inability to travel, all the activities related to the TS were postponed in agreement with the Project Officer (PO) to the M18 of the project. Also, minor adjustments in the timing and schedule of the lectures and workshops within the TS have been made, in response to the availability of facilities at the host institution, NANOFAC TS consortium members, lecturers and attendees. Finally, the event was scheduled for the week of June 27th-July 1st 2022.

Organization of the NANOFAC TS training school started in the months leading up to the event. The lecturers were selected to reflect the NANOFAC TS project objectives. The agenda of the NANOFAC TS Training School in Nanoparticles, and their application in cancer treatment, imaging, and sensing is presented in Fig. 1.

After settling the date and time of TS, particular attention was paid to the organization and promotion of the event, and arranging the travels and accommodation of the lecturers in Novi Sad and BIOS. The communication and promotion activities of the event intensified in the period M16 -M18. Special attention was devoted to attracting different target groups and informing them about the TS event. In order to boost the presence at the Training School, the announcement of the NANOFAC TS event is distributed through the project Website and NANOFAC TS Social media platforms (Figures 2- 5).

Different printed promotional materials, Fig. 6, were also prepared for exhibition and distribution to the various target groups of potential attendees. Thus, posters and leaflets about the NANOFAC TS were printed and distributed within the University of Novi Sad. In addition, leaflets and invitations were sent via e-mails to both individual researchers and targeted research groups and associations.

To promote TS to the general audience and the wider community, the team members of the NANOFAC TS project presented the basic idea of the project and the goals of the training school through participation at two national TV shows, Fig. 7, and through one statement in the national newspaper, Fig. 8.

The potential participants were asked to register via the WEB portal, Fig 2., with a purpose to have information about the number of interested participants in advance, which would help with the organization of the event. Nevertheless, the first three days of the event were open to all participants, regardless of whether they registered via the project's website or not.

TRAINING SCHOOL IN NANOPARTICLES,
THEIR APPLICATION IN CANCER TREATMENT, IMAGING AND SENSING

DEADLINE FOR APPLICATION: 15TH JUNE

START

nanofacts

Learn about cancer theranostics, cancer therapy and imaging using nanoparticles, MRI, biosensing of cancer, cancer biomarkers, microfluidic and magnetic cancer sensors, and much more in cancer-related topics

When: 27th June - 1st July 2022
Where: BioSense Institute
Rectorate Building & Science & Technology Park, Novi Sad

Free participation after application on www.nanofacts.net/training-school

PARTNERS:

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 942239

DAY 2 - TUESDAY, 28TH JUNE 2022

CANCER THERANOSTIC NANOMATERIALS

Location: Science & Technology park, UNS, Fruškogorska 1

09:30-10:25
Design of magnetic nanoarchitectures for cancer theranostics
Prof. Dr. Davide Peddis

10:25-11:20
Cancer prevention using magnetic nanoparticles
Dr. Oliviero Gobbo

11:20-12:15
Multifunctional nanoparticles for cancer imaging
Dr. Jelena Zinnanti

12:15-13:30
Lunch

13:30-14:25
Clinical aspects of cancer treatment
Dr. Igor Djan

14:25-15:20
Radiolabeled nanoparticles for the application in diagnosis and cancer treatment
Dr. Sanja Vranješ Djurić

15:20-16:15
The combined use of hydrogels and nanoparticles for the treatment of brain tumors
Dr. Binh T. Mai

DAY 1 - MONDAY, 27TH JUNE 2022

09:30-09:45
WELCOME ADDRESS
Location: Rectorate Building, UNS, Dr. Zorana Dindića 1

CANCER BIOSENSING AND IMAGING

09:45-10:40
NANOFACTS scientific concept: the application of mesoporous silica nanoparticles in cancer-related research
Dr. Nikola Knežević

10:40-11:35
Organ-on-a-chip applications in precision medicine
Prof. Dr. Peter Ertl

11:35-12:30
Magnetic biosensing for detection of biomarkers related to cancer and other pathologies
Prof. Dr. Paulo J. Peixeiro Freitas

12:30-14:00
Lunch

14:00-14:55
Cancer molecular biomarkers: from bench to application
Prof. Dr. Katarina Zeljić

14:55-15:50
Plasmonic detection of oncogenic DNA in liquid biopsy samples from colorectal cancer patients
Prof. Dr. Giuseppe Spoto

15:50-16:45
Multiplexing detection of biomarkers through SPR imaging and kinetics analysis
Dr. Francesco Floris

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DAY 3 - WEDNESDAY, 29TH JUNE 2022

Location: Science & Technology park, UNS, Fruškogorska 1

09:30-09:45
Basic skills Training: Teamwork and creative thinking
Prof. Dr. Nebojša Majstorović

11:00-12:00
Basic skills Training: Problem solving skills
Prof. Dr. Nebojša Majstorović

12:00-13:15
Lunch

13:15-14:10
EU Horizon programme for funding innovative ideas in the field of biomedicine
Prof. Dr. Goran Stojanović

14:10-15:05
Guidelines for project implementation
Jovana Vlaškalin

15:05-16:00
Creating and managing startups
Stavros Tsiouras

DAY 4 - THURSDAY, 30 TH JUNE 2022	
ONLY FOR THE NANOFAC TS CONSORTIUM WORKSHOPS: CANCER BIOSENSING	
Location: Rectorate Building, UNS, Dr. Zorana Dindića 1	
09:00-10:00	Workshop: In vitro assessment of therapeutic nanomaterials in 2D and 3D cell cultures, Day 1 Dr. Amelia Ultimo
10:00-11:00	Workshop: Preparation of composite biomaterials for biomedical application, Day 1 Dr. Thi Nga Tran
11:00-12:00	Rapid prototyping, Workshop: Microfluidic biosensors Prof. Dr. Peter Ertl
12:00-13:30	Lunch
13:30-15:00	NANOFAC TS consortium meeting
15:00-17:00	Workshop: Bio-chemical analyzer based on imaging surface plasmon resonance Eliana Manobianco and Dr. Francesco Floris

DAY 5 - FRIDAY, 1 ST JULY 2022	
ONLY FOR THE NANOFAC TS CONSORTIUM WORKSHOPS: CANCER THERANOSTICS	
Location: Rectorate Building, UNS, Dr. Zorana Dindića 1	
09:00-09:45	Nanosafety and the Regulatory Landscape (online lecture) Prof. Dr. Maria Santos-Martinez
09:45-10:30	Designing Animal Experiments Dr. Oliviero Gobbo
10:30-12:30	Workshop: In vitro assessment of therapeutic nanomaterials in 2D and 3D cell cultures, Day 2 Dr. Amelia Ultimo
12:30-14:00	Lunch
14:00-14:45	Sustainable CO ₂ -based biocomposites for active food packaging and biomedical applications Dr. Thi Nga Tran
14:45-16:45	Workshop: Preparation of composite biomaterials for biomedical application, Day 2 Dr. Thi Nga Tran

THANK YOU FOR PARTICIPATING
WE HOPE THAT YOU HAD FUN
LEARNING WITH US!

Figure 1: Agenda of NANOFAC TS Training school

The screenshot shows the website announcement for the 'TRAINING SCHOOL IN NANOPARTICLES, THEIR APPLICATION IN CANCER TREATMENT, IMAGING AND SENSING'. It features a central illustration of a person holding a large orange nanoparticle. A sign on the left says 'DEADLINE FOR APPLICATION: 15TH JUNE' and a sign on the right says 'START'. The website navigation bar includes 'HOME PAGE', 'ABOUT US', 'PARTICIPANTS', 'NEWS', 'TRAINING SCHOOL', 'PUBLICATIONS', and 'CONTACT'. Below the illustration, there is a text box with details about the event, including the topics to be covered, the dates (27th June - 1st July 2022), and the location (BioSense Institute Rectorate Building & Science & Technology Park, Novi Sad). A paragraph at the bottom describes the significance of nanotechnology in cancer treatment and the goals of the training school.

Figure 2: NANOFAC TS event announcement on Project website

Figure 3: NANOFACTS event announcement on Facebook

Figure 4: NANOFACTS event announcement on LinkedIn

Figure 5: NANOFAC TS event announcement on Twitter

Figure 6. Printed promo materials for NANOFAC TS event announcement: poster (left) and leaflet (right)

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JUN 2022

NANOFACTS on Serbian national television

Figure 7: NANOFACTS event announcements on TV

Figure 8: NANOFACTS event announcement in the newspaper.

2.2 NANOFACT Training school

Training School (TS) in Nanoparticles, their application in cancer treatment, imaging, and sensing was organized as an event comprising lectures and practical exercises in the period between the 27th of June and 1st of July 2022 in Novi Sad, Serbia. The event was organized at two locations within the campus of the University of Novi Sad, the Rectorate Building and Science & Technology Park.

The number of interested participants that registered for the event through the NANOFACTS webpage was 79, which included students, researchers and professors outside of NANOFACTS consortium and invited lecturers.

TS was organized in the following manner in accordance with the agenda in Fig. 1:

Day 1: The attendees were first welcomed by dr. Goran Kitić, Head of the Center for Sensing Technologies at the Biosense Institute (BIOS), with a brief introduction of the institute (Figure 9). Following his address, an introductory lecture about the NANOFACTS project and its scientific concept was given by the project PI (Dr. Nikola Knežević, Figure 10). This lecture covered the applicability of mesoporous silica-based nanomaterials (MSN) for devising theranostic modules for cancer treatment, as well as possibilities for utilizing

Figure 9 Welcome address by dr. Goran Kitić

MSN in devising biosensors for cancer biomarkers. The following 5 speakers on day 1 covered the topics related to the cancer biomarkers and construction of cancer-related biosensors.

Figure 10 lecture by dr. Nikola Knežević

Day 2 included seven lectures on the topics related to cancer theranostic nanomaterials, as well as clinical and surgical aspects of cancer treatment.

Day 3 was reserved for career building and training in basic researcher skills, such as teamwork, creative thinking, and problem-solving skills, as well as lectures on writing scientific project proposals, project implementation, and creating and managing of start-ups.

Day 4 consisted of workshops, with two workshops related to cancer biosensing and one workshop related to testing cancer theranostic nanoparticles on cells.

On **Day 5**, there was a second part of the workshop related to testing cancer theranostic nanoparticles on cells, workshop lectures related to research ethics and workshop focused on constructing composite biomaterials for biomedical applications.

2.3 Report on TS Lectures in cancer biosensing

The first day of the NANOFACCT TS event was reserved for the lecturers related to cancer biosensing and imaging. After the Welcome Address by dr. Goran Kitić, Head of the Center for Sensing Technologies at the Biosense Institute (BIOS), the project coordinator, **dr. Nikola Knezevic**, introduced the project with the lecture entitled: **"NANOFACCT scientific concept: the application of mesoporous silica nanoparticles in cancer-related research"**. The lecture was presented in the period 09:45-10:40 and different modalities for cancer theranostics and potentials for use of mesoporous silica nanoparticles in cancer biosensing were presented. After this lecture, there were 5 additional lectures covering the topics related to the construction, characterization, and testing of microfluidic and electronic, plasmonic, and magnetic biosensors for cancer diagnostics and detection of different biomolecules and cancer biomarkers. The lectures also included subjects such as microfluidic biosensors, organ-on-chip and its applications in medicine, and the application of nanoparticles in cancer research. The detail of each lecture, bibliography of the authors, abstract, date and schedule, and photos from the presentation are shown below.

Title	Organ-on-a-chip applications in precision medicine
Presenter	Prof. Dr. Peter Ertl
Institution	Vienna University of Technology (TUW), Faculty of Technical Chemistry, Institute of Applied Synthetic Chemistry and Institute of Chemical Technologies and Analytics
Date and time	27.06.2022 / 10:40 - 11:35
Abstract	The presentation provided an overview on existing organs-on-a-chip systems and their ability to recapitulate physiological-relevant microenvironments to study cell to cell and cell to matrix interactions in the context of health and disease. This was followed by an introduction into the state-of-the-art of personalized medicine and how patient-derived on-chip disease models can overcome current limitations of DNA-based precision medicine strategies. At the end of the lecture three examples using primary cells and iPSC-derived organoids were presented including therapy optimization for cancer therapy, drug optimization for rheumatic arthritis and Parkinson's diseases.
Golden Paragraph of presenter	Peter Ertl holds an engineering degree in Biotechnology (BOKU, Austria), a PhD in Chemistry (Univ. Waterloo, Canada) and received his postdoctoral training as a biophysicist at University of California at Berkeley (US). Additionally, in 2003 Dr. Ertl co-founded a biotech start-up company where he served a number of years as Director of Product Development in Kitchener-Waterloo (CAD) developing benchtop-sized cell analyzers. In 2005 Dr. Ertl moved to Austria where he worked as Senior Scientist in the BioSensor Technology unit at the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology. In 2016 he was appointed Professor for Lab-on-a-Chip Systems for Bioscience Technologies at the Faculty of Technical Chemistry of the Vienna University of Technology. Dr. Ertl was also granted a Fulbright Visiting Scholarship at UC Berkeley in 2011/2012 and conducted visiting scientist positions at Nanyang Technological University, Singapore in 2013 and the Medical Center of the University of California at San Francisco in 2014. In 2016 Dr. Ertl was appointed Professor for Lab-on-a-Chip Systems in Bioscience Technologies where his research focuses on the development of organ-on-a-chip and chip-in-organ systems for biomedical research. His current research endeavours aim at the integration of optical and electrical sensors, miniaturized fluid handling systems and electronic components into microfluidic devices to develop automated lab-on-a-chip systems for applications in biotechnology and medicine. The main focus of his research is the development of advanced organ-on-a-chip technologies, next-generation microfluidic devices for cell analysis and self-powered sensing applications as well as implantable biosensors and smart implants. A variety of technologies are employed to achieve those goals including rapid prototyping, such as hot embossing and replica molding; micromachining including

photolithography; material science aspects, including biocompatibilities, (bio)interfaces and (bio)functionalization methods; microfluidics including integrated pneumatic valves, micropumps, microdegassers and CFD simulations; as well as various biosensor technologies to monitor dynamic cell responses and activities.

Figure 11: The photos from the presentation of Dr. Peter Ertl.

Title	Magnetic biosensing for detection of biomarkers related to cancer and other pathologies
Presenter	Prof. Dr. Paulo J. Peixeiro Freitas
Institution	INL-International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory, Portugal
Date and time	27.06.2022 / 10:35 - 12:30
Abstract	<p>In this presentation we dr. Freitas introduced spintronic biochips, overview of the field and results for static multiplexed biomarkers detection in the last 20 years. The challenges in the field of cell free DNA detection in blood and μVesicle detection in serum as cancer biomarker, ICTUS related protein biomarkers for patient stratification, detection of colorectal cancer biomarkers in feces, simultaneous molecular (RNA) and serological (AB) probing in viral sample (Zika, Dengue, CV-19) will be presented and analyzed for the recent studies and different detection solutions.</p> <p>Recent results from his research group for multiplex detection of different biomarkers was enabled by developing MR biochip static platform with integrated microfluidic components, system for cell lysis and DNA extraction together with 30 sensing units. Different applications of the proposed platform were presented: brain eschemia biomarker from serum, CRC biomarker detection from stool, and cell free DNA detection as cancer biomarker. The biochip technology is based on the spintronic transducer deposited on the substrate and functionalized with DNA probes. After the hybridization with corresponding DNA, the target is labeled with labeled magnetic nanoparticles which show superparamagnetic properties. By measuring magnetic resistance, the sensor shows response for the detected specific sample.</p>
Golden Paragraph of presenter	<p>Prof. Dr. Paulo J. P. Freitas has a BSc in Physics from the University of Porto and a PhD in Physics from the Carnegie Mellon University (1986). After his PhD at the Carnegie Mellon University, he was a postdoctoral Research Fellow at the IBM Watson Research Center, Yorktown Heights, New York, USA (1986-87). From 1990 to 2000, he was Director of the Solid State Technology Group at INESC and since 2000, Director of INESC-MN. Professor Freitas has been a full professor of Physics at the Instituto Superior Técnico since 2003, administering the Department of Physics since 2006. In 2007, he joined the Installation Commission of the International Iberian Nanotechnology Institute (INL) and was appointed Deputy Director General</p>

in 2009. Professor Freitas received several awards and distinctions, namely: the Fundação Calouste Gulbenkian Prize in the area of Nanotechnologies, as PhD supervisor of H. Ferreira (2004); the Prémio Excelência, from the Portuguese Foundation for Science and Technology (2005-2006); the 2nd Finalist of Descartes Prize for Research (2007), awarded by The European Commission; and a Distinguished Lecturer award from the IEEE – Institute of Electrical and Electronic Engineers, USA (2008). Professor Freitas’ current research interests include GMR heads for ultra-high density recording, spin-dependent tunneling junctions, non-volatile memories, magnetic multilayers and thin films, micro magnetism, transport phenomena, GMR sensors, bioelectronics and biosensors. He is author of more than 250 scientific articles, one patent and inventor of a bioelectronic device. Professor Freitas supervised 9 PhD students and develops an intense educational mission to train and coach new scientists and engineers.

Figure 12: Presentation of Dr. Paulo J. Peixeiro Freitas

Title	Cancer molecular biomarkers: from bench to application
Presenter	Prof. Dr. Katrina Zeljic
Institution	Faculty of Biology, University of Belgrade, Serbia
Date and time	27.06.2022 / 14:00 - 14:55
Abstract	<p>A biomarker is defined as a “biological molecule found in blood, other body fluids, or tissues that is a sign of a normal or abnormal process, or of a condition or disease”. A biomarker can be used to predict how the body will react to a therapeutic intervention. Molecular biomarkers are a subgroup of biomarkers. Deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA), ribonucleic acid (RNA) or proteins are examples of molecular biomarkers.</p> <p>DNA molecular biomarkers can be various variations in a DNA molecule, such as single nucleotide polymorphisms, copy number variants, insertions and deletions, epigenetic changes, like DNA methylation, acetylation and so on. On the RNA level, RNA biomarkers for protein coding genes can be gene expression, different classes of non-coding RNA molecules (microRNA, long-non coding RNA, circular RNA etc). Protein biomarkers are numerous, and they can be level of enzymes or hormone levels in blood, body fluids, tissue. The protein level represents gene expression for a specific protein product in a biological specimen. A good molecular biomarker should be objectively and easily measured, stable and reliable, non-invasive, produce rapid and valuable results, and have high sensitivity and specificity. Cancer molecular biomarkers are molecules produced by cancer cells or their surroundings that can be used to detect cancerous processes in the body. Cancer molecular biomarkers fall into several categories and can be used for predictive, diagnostic, prognostic, and monitoring purposes. Many of so far identified and validated cancer molecular biomarkers have the clinical utility.</p> <p>Examples of cancer molecular biomarkers used in clinical practice were presented during the lecture. The process of translating findings from the bench to clinical</p>

	<p>application was explained. Furthermore, the findings of the discovery of micro RNA molecules that can be used as diagnostic and prognostic biomarkers in oral cancer were presented. The training school participants had the opportunity to ask questions and discuss the topic with the lecturer at the end of the lecture.</p>
<p>Golden Paragraph of presenter</p>	<p>Katarina Zeljić, PhD, Associate Professor in the Faculty of Biology at the University of Belgrade, has 12 years of extensive experience in molecular genetics and epigenetics of human pathologies, mainly cancer. Her research interest is mainly focused on molecular biomarkers in cancer, gene association studies – association of gene variants with cancer risk and non-coding RNAs. She obtained PhD from the Faculty of Biology – University of Belgrade in the field of molecular genetics of oral cancer. Since 2011, she has been employed in the Faculty of Biology of the University of Belgrade, first as a teaching associate, assistant, assistant professor, and associate professor since December 2017. Dr Zeljic is an independent professor for the courses Basics of medical genetics and Advanced medical genetics at undergraduate and master studies, respectively. She has supervised several masters and doctoral thesis. Dr Katarina Zeljic was trained at the Cancer Research Centre at the Karolinska Institute, Stockholm, Sweden in 2014 during her research visit. In 2013 she has been awarded by L’Oreal-UNESCO fellowship “For Women in Science” for outstanding achievements. Since July 2020, she is engaged as a research participant in the project SENSOGENE “Cancer biosensors based on gene regulatory elements” funded by the Science Fund of the Republic of Serbia within the PROMIS project. In June 2019, dr Katarina Zeljic has completed a master’s degree in bioethics, MSc specialization in research ethics, at Clarkson University, United States. She is the author of 30 scientific papers cited more than 400 times.</p>

Figure 13: The photos from the presentation of Dr. Katarina Zeljic

<p>Title</p>	<p>Plasmonic detection of oncogenic DNA in liquid biopsy samples from colorectal cancer patients</p>
<p>Presenter</p>	<p>Prof. Dr. Giuseppe Spoto</p>
<p>Institution</p>	<p>University of Catania, Italy.</p>
<p>Date and time</p>	<p>27.06.2022 / 14:55 - 15:50</p>
<p>Abstract</p>	<p>Standard clinical protocols for the evaluation of tumor profiling are usually based on tissue biopsy, which among several forms of direct tumor biopsy, consists of sampling cells from the human body using special needles or surgery. Tissue biopsy constitutes a significant barrier for easy and frequent monitoring of cancer patients and is subject to limitations including the difficulty in accounting for tumor cells heterogeneity. In liquid biopsy, biological fluids are instead sampled to monitor the level of cancer biomarkers available in biological fluids such as peripheral blood and</p>

	<p>blood-derived products such as plasma and serum. The detection of nucleic acid biomarkers for cancer diagnosis and patient follow-up based on liquid biopsy represents a challenging task for current biosensing platforms. Most of the biosensors used to detect nucleic acids exploit the enzymatic amplification of sequences to be identified to achieve the needed level of sensitivity. The amplification step introduces constraints and drawbacks in the assays. For instance, PCR suffers from artefacts generated by sample contamination and recombination between homologous regions of DNA.</p> <p>Efforts have been made to identify innovative PCR-free protocols for DNA detection. Most of such protocols exploit strategies for signal amplification based on the use of enzymes or metallic nanostructures. In particular, gold nanoparticles have been used to achieve the ultrasensitive detection of DNA. Possibilities offered by nanoparticle-enhanced surface plasmon resonance imaging (SPRI) in the detection of non-amplified human genomic DNA and DNA freely circulating in human blood will be discussed in the context of applications to cancer diagnosis based on liquid biopsy [1, 2]. The characteristics of functionalized nanoparticles for the effective nanoparticle-enhanced SPRI detection of DNA will be presented with specific attention to the role played by antifouling surface coatings in minimizing adverse effects caused by non-specific adsorption of plasma components on the sensing surfaces. A strategy based on the fabrication of dual-functional surface layers will be presented for the direct detection of KRAS mutated circulating tumor DNA in plasma sample from colorectal cancer patients.</p> <p>The presented work is part of ULTRAPLACAD Horizon 2020 (project n. 633937) and VerSiLiB Horizon Europe European Innovation Council (project n. 101046217) activities.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. D'Agata, R., Bellassai, N., Allegretti, M., Rozzi, A., Korom, S., Manicardi, A., Melucci, E., Pescarmona, E., Corradini, R., Giacomini, P., Spoto, G. <i>Biosensors and Bioelectronics</i>, 170, 2020, 112648 2. Noemi Bellassai, Roberta D'Agata, Almudena Marti, Andrea Rozzi, Stefano Volpi, Matteo Allegretti, Roberto Corradini, Patrizio Giacomini, Jurriaan Huskens, Giuseppe Spoto. <i>ACS Sensors</i>. 2021. 6(6), 2307–2319
<p>Golden Paragraph of presenter</p>	<p>Giuseppe Spoto is Professor of Analytical Chemistry at the University of Catania (Italy). He is also an executive committee member of the Biostructures and Biosystems National Institute (INBB) and board member of the Italian Chemical Society – Analytical Chemistry division. Giuseppe received his PhD in Chemical Sciences from the University of Catania. His primary research focuses on the development of innovative detection methods and assays. Plasmonic biosensing and microfluidics are today used in his lab to design new assays for the detection of biomarkers freely circulating in the blood of cancer patients. His research has been primarily supported by grants from the European Commission (running projects: AiPBAND, Horizon 2020 MSCA-ITN-2017; VerSiLiB, Horizon Europe EIC Pathfinder Open) and the Italian Ministry of Education, University and Research (MIUR) and he is the author and co-author of over 100 journal articles and book chapters. Giuseppe acted as the scientific coordinator of the ULTRAPLACAD (Ultrasensitive plasmonic devices for early cancer diagnosis) Horizon 2020 project, cited as an example of what Europe does for cancer patients in the portal “What Europe does for me” (European Parliamentary Research Service).</p>

Figure 14: The photos from the presentation of Dr. Giuseppe Spoto

Title	Multiplexing detection of biomarkers trough SPR imaging and kinetics analysis
Presenter	Dr. Francesco Floris
Institution	Physics Department of Pavia University, Italy
Date and time	27.06.2022 / 15:50 - 16:45
Abstract	The lecture was focused on the explanation of the main physics features of either localized and delocalized surface plasmon polaritons and their application in designing and optimizing a nanostructured plasmonic grating to perform surface plasmon resonance-based (SPR) measurements for bio-medical sensing application. The concept of thermodynamic analysis was presented as well as the main parameters related to kinetics, affinity, specificity, avidity, concentration, cross reactivity and inhibition together with multiplexing, imaging and real-time acquisition notions. Starting from the immunoassay preparation, the students were introduced to the identification of the best structures and configurations, reagents and recipes to improve the detection efficiency. Resorting to examples related to real measurements performed in several H200 projects, the behaviour of a typical experiment was shown. Some technical steps were also shown, such as the microarray pattern definition and preparation for tuning and refining the surface functionalization in relation also to combined SPR-SERS measurements for DNA test to better understand how to maximise the collection, storing and analysis of the final sensogram. The lecture was tailored to be also an introduction to the hands-on training offered during the following workshop, titled “Bio-chemical analyser based on imaging surface plasmon resonance”, carried in the BioSense laboratory within the same training school.
Golden Paragraph of presenter	Dr. Francesco Floris joined the Physics Department of Pavia University as Contract Researcher in 2022. His research activities are carried out in collaboration with Plasmore, a joint spin-off between Pavia University and the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission, mainly focused on the development and optimization of optoelectronic devices for bio-medical and agri-food applications. His hard skills span from spectroscopic and microscopy techniques, co-packaging design and optimization for opto-electronic devices and systems to computational models based on the finite-difference time-domain method. He previously worked at the Tyndall National Institute (UCC, Ireland) as Research Manager in the Photonics Packaging and Integration Group and at the University of Cagliari (Italy) as Didactical Tutor. He received his MSc. in Physics in 2012 and Ph.D. in Physics in 2016, both with

curricula of matter physics, from the University of Pavia (Italy) in the Optical Spectroscopy and Nanostructures Group. During his Ph.D., he also spent a semester at the Boston University (Massachusetts, USA) as Research Scholar thanks to an exchange programme prize of the Italian Ministry of Education, Universities and Research.

Figure 15: The photos from the presentation of Dr. Francesco Floris

In Total 52 participants attended the lectures on the first day of NANOFACCT training school related to cancer biosensing. The list of all participants is given in Appendix I of this document. Structure of participant was as follows:

- 23 students,
- 8 BIOS students,
- 26 researchers,
- 3 experts from the partners institutions,
- 6 external experts
- 15 BIOS researchers.

All the lectures were successful and greatly involved the presented audience, which resulted in a large number of questions and discussions during the lectures, but also in a number of face-to-face conversations with the presented after the end of their presentations.

2.3 Workshops in cancer biosensing

Workshops in cancer biosensing contained were organized on Day 4 of the NANOFAC TS event. Two training related to the rapid prototyping of the microfluidic biosensors, and biochemical analysis based on surface plasmon resonance. This part of the NANOFAC TS was reserved only for the BIOS stuff due to limited resources and lab capacity. Both trainings were organized as interactive events that encourage the participant to actively participate in each part of the training. The detail of each training, bibliography of the authors, abstract, date and schedule, and photos from the training are shown below.

Title	Rapid prototyping Workshop: Microfluidic biosensors
Presenter	Prof. Dr Peter Ertl
Institution	Vienna University of Technology (TUW), Faculty of Technical Chemistry, Institute of Applied Synthetic Chemistry and Institute of Chemical Technologies and Analytics
Date and time	30.06.2022 / 11:00 – 12:00
Abstract	The presentation was segmented into two parts where part I provided an overview on 3D tissue engineering strategies, animal testing and RRR (refine, reduce and replace) principles. This was followed by an exercise on how to standardize organ-on-a-chip system as a prerequisite for regulatory approval. Part II of the presentation was mainly concerned with engineering concepts by an in depth understanding of the design development process needed to go from idea to functional prototype to a marketable product. In addition to introducing a variety of rapid prototyping technologies needed to develop alpha-beta and gamma-prototypes some practical examples of engineering pitfalls during the design iteration phase were discussed.
Golden Paragraph of presenter	<p>Peter Ertl holds an engineering degree in Biotechnology (BOKU, Austria), a PhD in Chemistry (Univ. Waterloo, Canada) and received his postdoctoral training as a biophysicist at University of California at Berkeley (US). Additionally, in 2003 Dr. Ertl co-founded a biotech start-up company where he served a number of years as Director of Product Development in Kitchener-Waterloo (CAD) developing benchtop-sized cell analyzers. In 2005 Dr. Ertl moved to Austria where he worked as Senior Scientist in the BioSensor Technology unit at the AIT Austrian Institute of Technology. In 2016 he was appointed Professor for Lab-on-a-Chip Systems for Bioscience Technologies at the Faculty of Technical Chemistry of the Vienna University of Technology. Dr. Ertl was also granted a Fulbright Visiting Scholarship at UC Berkeley in 2011/2012 and conducted visiting scientist positions at Nanyang Technological University, Singapore in 2013 and the Medical Center of the University of California at San Francisco in 2014. In 2016 Dr. Ertl was appointed Professor for Lab-on-a-Chip Systems in Bioscience Technologies where his research focuses on the development of organ-on-a-chip and chip-in-organ systems for biomedical research. His current research endeavours aim at the integration of optical and electrical sensors, miniaturized fluid handling systems and electronic components into microfluidic devices to develop automated lab-on-a-chip systems for applications in biotechnology and medicine. The main focus of my research is the development of advanced organ-on-a-chip technologies, next-generation microfluidic devices for cell analysis and self-powered sensing applications as well as implantable biosensors and smart implants.</p> <p>A variety of technologies are employed to achieve those goals including rapid prototyping, such as hot embossing and replica molding; micromachining including photolithography; material science aspects, including biocompatibilities, (bio)interfaces and (bio)functionalization methods; microfluidics including integrated pneumatic valves, micropumps, microdegassers and CFD simulations; as well as various biosensor technologies to monitor dynamic cell responses and activities.</p>

Figure 16: The photos from the training in Rapid prototyping Workshop: Microfluidic biosensors

Title	Bio-chemical analyser based on imaging surface plasmon resonance
Presenter	Eliana Manobianco and Francesco Floris
Institution	Physics Department of Pavia University, Plasmore, Italy
Date and time	27.06.2022 / 15:00 - 17:00
Abstract	<p>The workshop was divided in two parts, a theoretical one in which the principles and practical tools needed to perform an experiment using an imaging-SPR instrument were explained, and practical one in which students were involved in the experimental part.</p> <p>The presentation started with an introduction to the principle by which the surfaces developed at Plasmore have unique properties as platforms for performing biochemical assays. The iNPx instrument components as well as the software features were presented in the framework of the set-up of a typical experiment. After concluding the introduction on the instrument followed the discussion on the functionalization of the nanostructured surfaces comprising the polymer coating</p>

	<p>procedure and the immobilization of the biomolecules by mean of a spotter. In conclusion, concepts on the potential of different modalities to perform biological analysis were exposed, bringing as an example the detection of oligonucleotides. The various steps of performing binding tests and surface regeneration were discussed and results from a real case were displayed. At the end of the presentation some students were involved in the preparation of solutions for the analysis and were able to get hands-on experience on the main steps in setting up a measurement, to finally see the results of the biochemical recognition event with an imaging system.</p>
<p>Golden Paragraph of presenter</p>	<p>Dr. Francesco Floris joined the Physics Department of Pavia University as Contract Researcher in 2022. His research activities are carried out in collaboration with Plasmore, a joint spin-off between Pavia University and the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission, mainly focused on the development and optimization of optoelectronic devices for bio-medical and agri-food applications. His hard skills span from spectroscopic and microscopy techniques, co-packaging design and optimization for opto-electronic devices and systems to computational models based on the finite-difference time-domain method. He previously worked at the Tyndall National Institute (UCC, Ireland) as Research Manager in the Photonics Packaging and Integration Group and at the University of Cagliari (Italy) as Didactical Tutor. He received his MSc. in Physics in 2012 and Ph.D. in Physics in 2016, both with curricula of matter physics, from the University of Pavia (Italy) in the Optical Spectroscopy and Nanostructures Group. During his Ph.D., he also spent a semester at the Boston University (Massachusetts, USA) as Research Scholar thanks to an exchange programme prize of the Italian Ministry of Education, Universities and Research.</p> <p>Elina Monobianco is graduated in Advance Biotechnology from the University of Pavia. She has experience in biochemistry methods and polymer synthesis. In Plasmore she collaborates for the biofunctionalization of nanoplasmonic surface at the bioassays development.</p>

Figure 17: The photos from the training in Bio-chemical analyser based on imaging surface plasmon resonance

In Total 33 participants participated in training related to cancer biosensing. The list of all participants is given in Appendix I of this document. The structure of participants was as follows:

- 27 BIOS staff,
- 13 BIOS students,
- 14 BIOS senior researchers,
- 1 BIOS technician,
- 2 TCD researchers.

Conclusions

In cooperation with the project partners, Trinity College Dublin (TCD), Ireland, and Vienna University of Technology (TUW), the BioSense Institute (BIOS), Serbia organized the NANOFAC T Training School in Nanoparticles, their application in cancer treatment, imaging, and sensing. The Training School comprises lectures and practical training in the period between the 27th of June and the 1st of July 2022 at the BioSense Institute in Novi Sad, Serbia.

During the five-day event, a total of 21 lectures, 4 workshops, and 1 consortium meeting were held. The NANOFAC T S enabled a transfer of knowledge from project partners, invited speakers, and international experts to students, researchers, and young professionals on scientific advances related to the development of cancer biosensors, development of nanomaterials for targeted therapy and imaging of cancer, clinical and surgical aspects of cancer treatment and about cancer biomarkers. A special part of the NANOFAC T S was dedicated to the lectures related to soft skills such as creative thinking, teamwork, and problem-solving skills and lectures related to writing scientific project proposals, project implementation, and start-up management. Lectures related to ethics in working with nanomaterials and animals were also presented during the Workshop training on the fifth day.

The average number of participants present at the lectures during all three lecturers' days was 50, while 33 participants attended the workshops on the first WS day and 30 on the second one, which fulfilled the planned KPI indicators for the NANOFAC T project related to the TS. This event was also providing a significant opportunity for scientific networking through face-to-face communication among scientists with different backgrounds, between scientists and industrial partners from Plasmore, between partners researchers and students, and the general public. Based on all the indicators, we can conclude that NANOFAC T Training School in nanoparticles, their application in cancer treatment, imaging, and sensing was successfully organized and implemented in accordance with the objectives and goals of the project.

Appendix I - List of participants at the NANOFACT training school

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 27. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/researcher/professor/other...)	Institution
1.	Marko Radović	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
2.	Jelena Dović	student	FTN
3.	Nina Eretović	student	FTN
4.	Ivana Miličić	student	FTN
5.	Jovana Kalamković	student	FTN
6.	Lazar Milić	student	FTN
7.	Pete Eik	visiting scholar	TUW
8.	Bojana Blagojević	researcher	faculty of Agriculture Novi Sad
9.	Ruzica Zolner Kulović	researcher	- - -
10.	Boris Popović	Full professor	Faculty of Agriculture NS
11.	Vesna Teofilović	Researcher	TF NS
12.	Miroslav Dočoš	student	FTN
13.	Manija Vejin	student	FTN
14.	Evgen Bobrinetskiy	researcher	Biosense
15.	Manil Kukkar	Researcher	Biosense
16.	Ksenija Stanojević	student	FTN
17.	Marko Vikić	student	FTN
18.	Dušan Radonić	student	PMF
19.	Dušan Žirković	student	PMF
20.	Tilmanja Ulečić	Researcher	PMF NS
21.	Nejra Omerović	Junior Researcher	Biosense

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACETS 27. 6. 2022.

22.	Ida Zahović	Researcher	TF NS
23.	Dajana Lužarević	Researcher	Vinča Institute
24.	JASKINA MURVIĆ	Researcher	Vinča Institute
25.	IRENA MILER	Researcher	BioSense
26.	FRANCESCO FLORIS	Researcher	PLASTORE
27.	MARIA BARBARA RACCIONI	Researcher	PLASTORE
28.	MAVINO PORNIS	PROFESSOR	UNIGE
29.	DANIJELA PETROVIĆ GRADVAČ	PROFESSOR	UNS
30.	GRIGORIJA ŽUPUT	Researcher	BioSense
31.	Biljana Favić	FOOD ENGINEERING RESEARCHER	FACULTY OF TECHNOLOGY NOVI SAD
32.	OLIVIERO COBBO	Researcher	TCD
33.	Binh T. Mai	Research Fellow	TCD
34.	Nikolina Janković	Researcher	BioSense
35.	Ivana Podinavac	Junior researcher	BioSense
36.	NIKOLA KNEŽEVIĆ	SENIOR RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
37.	MINJA MLADENOVIĆ	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE INSTITUTE
38.	Jovana Stanojević	Researcher	BioSense Institute
39.	Sara Joksović	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	BioSense Institute
40.	Čirko Čobek	Junior researcher	BioSense Institute
41.	Nerenda Jakićević HEBETA JAKIMOVIĆ	student	Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy
42.	Mumya Tetka	student	Science Faculty
43.	Gorana Ilić	student	Faculty of sciences

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACETS 27. 6. 2022.

44.	JELENA RADEVIĆ	STUDENT	FACULTY OF SCIENCES
45.	Teodora Despotovski	student	Faculty of Sciences
46.	KATARINA ŽEJIC	PREDAVAČ	FACULTY OF BIOLOGY UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE
47.	Aleksandra Jakobović	Junior ^{research} Assistant	BIOSENSE
48.	Paulo FREITAS	PROFESSOR	INL
49.	GIUSEPPE SPOTO	PROFESSOR	UNIVERSITY OF CATANIA
50.	STEFAN JAPUN	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BIOSENSE
51.	Mila Disalou	JUNIOR RESEARCH assistant	BioSense
52.	PETAR DAVIDOVIĆ	RESEARCH ASSISTANT	FACULTY OF SCIENCES NOVI SAD
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ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACETS 30. 6. 2022.

No.	Name	Occupation (student/manager/researcher/professor/other...)	Institution
1.	AMELIA UTIMO	RESEARCHER	TCD
2.	O. Cobbo	Researcher	TCD
3.	Ivana Podunavac	Junior researcher	BioSense
4.	Nejra Omerović	Junior researcher	BioSense Institute
5.	СТЕФАН ЈАРЉИЋ	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BIOSENSE
6.	Nevena Jaćimović	Student	Faculty of Technology and Metallurgy, Belgrade
7.	Mila Disabov	JUNIOR RESEARCH ASSISTANT	BioSense Institute
8.	Bara Joksović	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	BioSense Institute
9.	Aleksandra Habrović	Junior research assistant	BioSense Institute
10.	Nikolina Janković	Researcher	BioSense
11.	IRENA MIKER	Researcher	BioSense
12.	Ivan Poljinec	Researcher	BIOSENSE
13.	FRANJA DRAGIĆ	Researcher	PLASTORE
14.	FRANCESCO FLORII	RESEARCHER	PLASTORE
15.	George Dubov	Researcher BioSense	
16.	Димитрија Димитријевић	Junior Research Assistant	dimityr
17.	MINJA MAČENOVIĆ	JUNIOR RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE INSTITUTE
18.	Čestimir Čelić	Senior researcher	BIOSENSE INSTITUTE
19.	Marić Kukica	Researcher	BioSense
20.	MARJANA	RESEARCHER	BIOSENSE
21.	MARCO PAVIĆ	Researcher	BioSense

ATTENDANCE LIST
Training school NANOFACTS 30. 6. 2022.

22.	Dušan Žilbović	Student	PMF
23.	Nikola Kavcenič	SENIOR RESEARCHER	BIOS
24.	Črdenja Čelik	senior researcher	BIOS
25.	Milena Jazbec	Researcher	BIOS
26.	Željko Gynty	Other	BIOS
27.	Maura Džepić	Researcher	BIOS
28.	Alma Kizore	Researcher	BIOS
29.	Herman Kumar R.R.	Researcher	BIOS
30.	J.S.	RESEARCHER	BIOS
31.	Josip Cyl	RESEARCHER	BIOS
32.	Branimir Pijec	RESEARCHER	BIOS
33.	Jan Ožek	RESEARCHER	BIOS
34.			
35.			
36.			